

How to beat the Pandemic downturn- Strategy of Proctor & Gamble amid the crisis

Dr. Monirul Islam

*Assistant Professor of Marketing Management
Xavier Business School (XBS), St Xavier's University, Kolkata, India
E-mail: moni05081985@gmail.com*

ABSTRACT

COVID-19 has already had a huge impact on companies, customers and types. The stay-at-home directives, radical shifts in demand sure as shooting product classes, undersupplied distribution channels, and provide chain difficulties sure as shooting firms have non-continuous habitual behaviors and needed customers to buy in new ways that. This is important for brands, particularly market leaders in their classes, as a result of human square measure psychological feature misers, which means that we have a tendency to use mental shortcuts to guide the judgments and choices. In terms of buying behavior, once a routine in a very sure store or preference for specific complete is established, it becomes habitual and is tough to vary. In traditional times, gaining consumers' attention and moving the needle on key consumer-behavior metrics was an expensive endeavor and infrequently on the far side the budgets and selling capabilities of the many little and mid-tier brands.

The current atmosphere offers associate degree unexampled chance for these FMCG firms to contend against their tried and true rivals for exposure, mindshare, product trials, and market share with a brand new and broader base of potential customers. The principle objective of this article, is to share the findings of proper analysis into what P & G is strategizing it's marketing proportion of shopper purchases is prone to substitution and therefore the ways that brands will rethink their worth propositions to customers in unsure times.

Key words: Marketing strategy, economic downturn, FMCG, marketing mix

INTRODUCTION

The world remains to experience a pestilence because of the extremely infectious virus referred to as the coronavirus, or COVID- nineteen. In an endeavour to slow the unfold of the virus, several countries in the entire world have obligatory temporary closures to non-essential stores and completely different venues to place a ban on giant public gatherings and inspiring folks to maximize work from home where attainable. The marketplace for FMCG's long-faced tidy changes i.e., the demand for consumer-packaged goods (CPG) has escalated sharply in extremely affected countries, whereas growth in social unit merchandise disbursal surged moreover. This statement has been even for the FMCG sector in 2020 because the whole world struggled to combat the COVID- nineteen Pandemic.

The recent and still ongoing Pandemic accompanied with the all-time negative performance of India's GDP and volatile economic and competitive conditions have augmented the need to re-examine the standardization and / or adaptation strategy. Henceforth, the study attempts to provide such a framework which creates the factors related to the decision of assortment of adaptation or standardization strategy in the company marketing mix affecting the sustainability during crisis and the competition of a firm. It is implicit that this will enhance to the progress of empirical research about this topic.

People have tried to cut back their possibilities of catching the virus is by decreasing the frequency of going to resolute grocery stores. shoppers are resorting to warehousing water and food. The others have purchased merchandise from e-commerce websites that they typically will notice in an exceedingly general food market.

Coronavirus has expected advertisers to re-examine how their organizations go to showcase and draw in with clients. Those advertisers who can use advanced, social and believed connections ought to be all around situated to explore continuous interruptions. Nonetheless, advertisers across all ventures should move past emergency the board to accept exercises and research botched freedoms to make more an incentive for their clients and organizations. Keeping that in mind, the exercises shared here are offered to assist advertisers with recognizing regions they need to improve.

While much-remaining parts obscure about the months ahead, we feel sure that COVID-19 will be an essential time for advertisers, empowering them to fill in as individual planners and esteemed accomplices in the C-suite as they sanction their organizations' prospects.

P&G was established quite a hundred and eighty years back as an easy cleansing agent and lightweight organization. Today, P&G is that the world's greatest client things association and residential to notorious trustworthy brands that create life fairly less advanced in very little anyway vast habits. P&G has traversed 3 centuries with most extreme: initiative, advancement and citizenship. The understanding, development and enthusiasm of precocious teams has aided P&G with growing a worldwide organization that's administered competently and virtuously, that's open and easy, which upholds nice motivations and ensures the climate

P&G's sixty-five individual brands are organized into ten product classes.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

Data and Sample

For data collection regarding theoretical basics and review of literature, library studies, required articles and books were used.

Deductive research approach has been used which includes various secondary data collection methods. The Data has been collected from various Published & Unpublished Journals, Articles, Magazines, and information available in various popular and related websites, popular Journals, Text Books etc. which focused on various aspects and concepts of Adoption & Standardization of Marketing Strategies

The methodology used for this research is Secondary Data. The data has been taken from various journals, company websites, business documents, books etc.

Marketing Strategies of P&G during Covid- 19

Small and mid-tier brands have distinctive opportunities to produce worth within the new shopper atmosphere.

Procter & Gamble, the FMCG company manufacturer is seeking to maintain its focus on consumer insight & brand building in response to the COVID- 19 pandemic, and the financial challenges that are likely to follow. Procter & Gamble has aimed to use the pandemic to build on a strategy that increases productivity and builds long- term success for its brands. The CFO of P&G Jon Moeller has said that "To succeed during the COVID- 19 Pandemic, companies need to push forward not push back.

He said the company's strategy was "unwavering" & that P&G had a bright future despite the difficulties of coronavirus pandemic. P&G's products have always & special during the COVID-19 Pandemic, the products have played an essential role as people spent more on cleaning, household products. P&G has focused on 'constructive disruption' prioritizing disruption across the entire business, including marketing & the supply chains, as it seeks to be more productive. The CFO explained that the short term needs to balance the pandemic crisis & the long-term need to invest in top & bottom-line growth underscore the importance of productivity.

This FMCG giant has discovered new ways to be productive daily as it adapts & streamlines its business due to the coronavirus pandemic. However, the CFO believed that these changes will lead to positive long- term effects on the company.

In support of individuals wherever who are really focusing on their families and networks – the entire day, consistently, P&G individuals are venturing up and serving others as a power for great.

P&G brought up confident brands that help individuals clean, deal with their own wellbeing and cleanliness, and make sound homes for their families. P&G is serving networks comprehensively with the time, ability and specialized capacity.

In this extraordinary time, all that P&G has done was guided by three centre standards:

- Securing the wellbeing and prosperity of P&G individuals;
- Serving purchasers around the planet who rely on the brands and the advantages they give;
- Supporting people group, help organizations and individuals who are on the cutting edges of this worldwide pandemic.

- Taken together, they guarantee P&G will be there for the representatives, shoppers and networks who have consistently been there for P&G.

Keeping Employees Safe

P&G individuals invest heavily in each part of planning, making and conveying the boss items for customers. Altogether cases, we will guarantee the security of the workplaces and assurance of the kin — this is the first concern. P&G's Purpose, Values and Principles fill in as the guide, as they have for ages.

With direction from clinical experts, we're continually assessing and refreshing the strong estimates effectively set up to help the kin who are making, pressing and transportation P&G items stay protected at work. This incorporates temperature checks, move pivots, queueing shirking, and physical removing where conceivable. We're performing exhaustive, efficient cleaning of all creation zones, including normal sterilization and surface purification that surpasses the most thorough wellbeing authority principles.

We're likewise preparing and urging all workers to make savvy, fitting decisions, for example, remaining at home if they feel unwell, are essential for high-hazard gatherings, or have prior ailments. Taking all things together cases, we join forces with the workers separately and proactively to guarantee they feel — and are — ensured and protected to serve the buyers, clients, and networks. This has never been more significant, as a large number of the offices are going nonstop to convey the items during this time of expanded interest.

The industry-driving advantages plans assume a basic part in giving P&G individuals the assets they need to really focus on themselves and their families. From paid leave and thorough clinical consideration to adaptable work game plans and monetary help, P&G individuals can work unquestionably realizing the Company remains with and behind them consistently — however particularly during seasons of emergency. It's moving to observe the numerous demonstrations of administration individuals are taking to help and really focus on one another, exhibiting inventiveness, adaptability, and responsibility — genuinely P&G at the best.

Serving the consumers

Numerous P&G items are vital to forestall the spread of COVID-19 around the globe, especially those that are utilized day by day for cleaning and disinfecting homes, organizations and spots like medical care and helped living offices.

Other P&G items are basic for assisting shoppers with keeping up legitimate cleanliness, individual wellbeing and solid home conditions.

Everybody at P&G is working constantly to keep up the creation, conveyance and accessibility of every one of the brands, for buyers as well as for the solace and certainty of the clinical experts and people on call who are on the bleeding edge of the fight against COVID-19.

Supporting Communities

Beyond the brands, we have a long history of supporting networks amid hardship — and we are noting the call to do considerably more. We're venturing up to give truly necessary item gifts and monetary help. We're joining forces with and supporting more than 200 NGOs, help offices and a portion of the world's driving alleviation associations. The commitments of the item and in-kind help are during the many millions and will keep on expanding as we work with networks around the globe to see how we can best serve them.

A large number of P&G items are being given from more than 30 brands more than 30 nations, with additional in transit. These gifts help guarantee that families who don't have fundamental admittance to the ordinary basics a significant number of us underestimate, can have the cleaning, wellbeing and cleanliness benefits P&G brands can give.

P&G steps up in Europe with Donations & Aid

On Friday, P&G in Europe reported we're making gifts adding up to \$10 million in items and monetary help toward aid ventures for the #COVID19 reaction. This critical gift permits us to convey ordinary cleaning, wellbeing and cleanliness fundamentals to the individuals who need it most.

The accomplice International Federation of Red Cross and Red Crescent Societies will guide \$1 million of this gift to improve the existences of weak individuals across the mainland during these difficult occasions. We are likewise working with Red Cross and Red Crescent National Societies and nearby food banks to give ordinary fundamentals to individuals out of luck, particularly families, old residents and wellbeing experts.

These gifts characterize how P&G has supported the networks as a #ForceForGood.

Hand Sanitizer to battle COVID-19

P&G has put in new lines to begin the creation of hand sanitiser in five assembling destinations around the globe, utilizing it to guarantee the kin can keep working securely and offering it to emergency clinics, wellbeing specialists and help associations. P&G is extending producing limit further in extra offices in the coming weeks and will have a limit of in any event 45,000 litres each week when completely operational.

Manufacturing Masks

Work is in progress to deliver fundamentally required face veils at almost twelve P&G producing locales around the globe. We're fully operational effectively in China. We have groups attempting to introduce limit in North America, Europe, and the Asia Pacific, Middle East and Africa, and will rapidly start creation in the coming weeks. This is significant for a few reasons:

- It will build the stockpile of veils for medical clinics, people on the call and different associations by diminishing business sector interest for the creation and mechanical use;
- It causes us to establish a protected workspace for P&G individuals;
- Long term, it will permit us to straightforwardly help numerous networks across the globe where there is a remarkable requirement for defensive supplies.

FINDINGS AND ANALYSIS

As an organization's meet-and-welcome capacity, showcasing's most significant occupation is to distinguish, draw in with and convert clients into important resources that make long haul money streams. This job has been overturned during COVID-19. Advertisers have needed to reevaluate their methodologies in a period of homebound clients, social removing, and a capricious climate that has constrained numerous organizations into an emergency on the board. As the pandemic continues, both organizations have changed showcasing techniques to the isolate mode. Minor or major, changes have been made to activity hours, client correspondence, spending assignment, new item deliveries, and arranging.

From the above general and marketing strategies took up by both the FMCG brands, Dabur & Procter & Gamble, we have seen the common factors in both during the COVID- 19 Pandemic & these are as follows: -

- E-commerce
- Advanced Delivery & payments
- Enhanced Shipping mode
- Access to paid content
- Growth of Content volume
- Social & charity campaigns
- Anti- crisis offers
- Paid/ Unpaid collaborations
- The online experience of products
- Adapted Marketing Communication

The four key pillars are:

1. Use pricing to maintain and strengthen brand portfolio
2. Invest in marketing and advertising to strengthen 'mental availability'
3. Adopt a shopper-led meticulous approach to holistically understand customers
4. Streamline, rationalise and innovate overall product range

Email Marketing During COVID-19 Pandemic Crisis

- The COVID-19 email advertising has been experiencing the accompanying stages:
- alert COVID-19 messages (store conclusion, working hours, merchandise exchange changes). That was the briefest stage as most brands before long went to other correspondence channels like SMS and Mob Push to send news and short warnings.
- we're-in-it-together messages (wellbeing matters, we care about the workers, we're here for you, we'll adapt to everything together). Hardly any brands sent none of such messages: the majority of them appeared to be identical, utilized a similar language, and contained minimal reasonable data. Their wealth and similarity in the long run brought about inconvenience and disturbance as opposed to planned help and numerous brands halted such missions.

- access to content (free downloads, motion pictures, music, assets, online courses, classes, virtual visits, shows, mastery). The measure of the offered data before long got overpowering: it's difficult to process even one 10th of the out of nowhere accessible substance regardless of how helpful it is. In any case, the training is a decent special apparatus and numerous brands continue utilizing it.
- social responsibility (gifts, the backing of nearby networks, help for cutting edge labourers, chipping in). In these tough situations, no assistance is excessive. Such missions remain and will stay applicable insofar as planned appropriately. The spotlight ought to be not on YOU (we did, we made, we accomplished, on account of us, it was us who) however on real assistance, individuals who got it and ways for others to join the impetuses.
- entertainment (#self-disconnection and #stayhome challenges, uplifting news, positive insights, client-created stories, how to keep yourself occupied with during the isolate). Individuals are burnt out on death case numbers, joblessness rates, and relentless stricter guidelines. What many need to find in the inbox today is something that helps stay diverted and busy with other than COVID-19.
- plans for the future (what you will do when everything is finished). No one can anticipate anything nowadays, however, a few brands are beginning to offer you to fantasize about a post-isolate time. Such missions require a cautious methodology yet generally can be joined in the promoting plan.

Social Campaigns

Compassion and backing are fundamental for these days showcasing plan, including email crusades. There's no compelling reason to commend the devotion and exertion in each message. In any case, mention to your clients how you're doing assist the local area with exploring the emergency. It will fill in as a proof that they've settled on the correct decision placing their trust in the image, also, to help spread the word and connect more individuals willing to partake in whatever you're running. This includes

- social initiatives;
- support for local communities;
- support of frontline workers;
- donation;
- charitable collaborations.
- Volunteering

MANAGERIAL IMPLICATIONS

The major Indian economic sectors as well as China, the USA, Asian Nation and plenty of European nations (EU), area unit subject to total or partial closure. The epidemic has wreaked mayhem and havoc on the individuals and the economy of those countries

Managerially, owing to progressively global competitive and economic compressions more business entities are enforced to globalise or acclimatize their respective marketing strategy. As a result, managers are restraints to transform the way in which they operate their business and marketing strategy to compete efficiently in the domestic as well as global arena. In this crisis, it would be a mammoth & risky task whether to standardize a FMCG company marketing mix around the world or adapt it to prevailing local conditions. This become more complex to decide whether it would be more appropriate to follow a marketing strategy based on standardisation or adaptation framework.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Finally, aforementioned phenomenon and strategies adopted by P & G reflects to draw a framework to demonstrates the impact of pandemic crisis as the independent variable and the factors related to strategy for standardization or adaptation in the FMCG company's marketing strategy. Moreover, it is anticipated that this framework will augment to the progress of empirical research on this and allied topic which will, in turn, lead to the improvement of business marketing strategy. The biggest outcome of the COVID- nineteen Pandemic was the step-up within the adoption of digital media by FMCG firms not just for distribution purposes however additionally for stigmatization, promoting, and advertising their product. There has been a tectonic shift towards online owing to the numerous feature of this internment because of the COVID- nineteen. The COVID-19 Pandemic has had a big impact on client behaviour particularly once it involves FMCG searching. The FMCG firms each massive and little- that have designed expansive distribution networks through small

Kirana outlets and supermarkets and in line with them the internment has helped them provide online sales as shoppers stuck reception turned to shop for necessities on the web.

CONCLUSIONS

These strategic pillars of growth can facilitate FMCG retailers and types to attain the goal of sustained growth throughout this era. The muse of the four key pillars has the aim to assist retailers and types direct prices to take a position in daring new opportunities.

Indian shopper FMCG defrayal is a smaller amount discretionary than alternative varieties of defrayal. for instance, individuals should purchase food despite economic conditions. this suggests that it's additional recession-proof than alternative industries. The instinct among loads of companies are to retreat and defend their revenue, however to thrive firms have to be compelled to get out of their comfort to explore the probabilities. The demand for product necessary to daily living sustains itself throughout recessions and crisis amount. As a result, businesses may position their product as necessary expenses will manage the downswing well.

REFERENCES

- [1]. Dekimpe, M. G., & Deleersnyder, B. (2018). Business cycle research in marketing: A review and a research agenda. *Journal of the Academy of Marketing Science*, 46(1), 31–58.
- [2]. Deleersnyder, B., Dekimpe, M. G., Steenkamp, J.-B. E. M., & Leeflang, P. S. H. (2009). The role of national culture in advertising's sensitivity to business cycles: An investigation across continents. *Journal of Marketing Research*, 46(5), 623–636.
- [3]. Euromonitor International. (2020a). How is COVID-19 affecting the top 10 global consumer trends 2020? April 2020.
- [4]. Euromonitor International. (2020b). How will consumer markets evolve after coronavirus? June 2020.
- [5]. Steimer, S. (2020). How marketers are working during the pandemic. *Marketing News*, Spring. Accessible at <https://www.ama.org/marketing-news/how-marketers-are-working-during-the-pandemic/>.